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Orff Schulwerk
and Pop Culture:
Trending Now

The Role of Popular Music in the Schulwerk

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ABSTRACT

Music from children’s culture and elemental compositions form the central canon of the Orff Schulwerk approach. In this article, the author explains why popular music is also “music for children” today, describes the elemental characteristics of popular music that invite creativity, and offers strategies for bringing popular music into the Orff Schulwerk classroom.

By Martina Vasil

Music from children’s culture and original compositions are the canon of the Orff-Schulwerk approach (Orff, 1963). When Carl Orff and Gunild Keetman began developing the Schulwerk, they recognized the potential of children’s natural play, spontaneity, and music making for developing musicality and musical understanding. Hence, playground chants and songs, lullabies, folk, and elemental music are at the core of the *Music for Children* volumes (Orff, 1963). Although many materials from the Volumes remain relevant to today’s children, other pieces are not as familiar or pertinent as they once were. Orff teachers across the United States continue to evolve and adapt their Schulwerk practices and repertoire to reflect the cultural make-up of their classrooms. Popular music is arguably more familiar and culturally relevant to children today than much folk material because it is more closely aligned with their everyday experiences and musical preferences (Doyle, 2012). It is often elemental in nature and is a positive addition to the Schulwerk.

Defining Popular Music

Popular music may be described as a specific genre within the realm of contemporary music (i.e., Justin Bieber sings “pop” music) (Pop, 2019), or

it can be used to include a vast diversity of music genres that are appealing to the masses and have broad commercial appeal (Popular Music, 2019). For the purpose of this article, popular music is defined as music that is mass-consumed and develops with each generation of youths as newer popular styles replace older ones (Green, 2006; Mark 1994/2010; Rodriguez, 2004). Mass-consumption can be measured by Billboard chart rankings, how much revenue the music generates, whether it is sold as sheet music or used in soundtracks, or how prevalent it is across social media platforms (Green, 2006; Mark 1994/2010; Rodriguez, 2004). Popular music can embrace a variety of styles and genres and look different depending on the creating and listening contexts.

Popular Music and Orff Schulwerk

What role should popular music play in today's Orff Schulwerk classroom? Some Orff teachers embrace popular music, whereas others argue there is no room in their already-packed curriculum or that popular music is not high-quality enough to be part of a child's music education. Nevertheless, the characteristics and philosophy of Orff Schulwerk and typical popular music education overlap in many areas: learning processes, teaching characteristics, music from children's cultures, musical characteristics, and creativity.

Learning processes

Researchers have studied how popular musicians learn (Campbell, 1995; Davis, 2005; Green, 2002). Learning processes that researchers of popular music education have identified overlap with learning processes in Orff Schulwerk classrooms (Lawton, 2019; Vasil, 2019). First, an air of inclusivity, the idea that everyone is musical and should be included in music education, is apparent in both Orff Schulwerk and popular music education. These are not auditioned music classes. Everyone is welcomed and celebrated. Second, Orff Schulwerk teachers encourage musical exploration and co-constructing content, acting as facilitators of the music-making process. Third, in both popular music and Orff classrooms, students primarily learn music aurally through listening and imitation. Popular musicians may work to imitate their favorite artists, whereas children are often imitating the teacher, who acts as the model. Last, Orff Schulwerk teachers often

use self-directed and peer-learning strategies for processing materials and solving musical problems (Vasil, 2019). This kind of inclusive, accessible music learning environment invites collaborative musical exploration and creation while simultaneously developing aural and performance skills, a scene familiar to Orff Schulwerk teachers.

Teaching characteristics

Green (2008) studied how the role of the teacher changes once popular music and the processes for learning and creating popular music are brought into classrooms. As with the learning processes, the characteristics of popular music teachers and Orff Schulwerk teachers overlap (Vasil, 2019). The Orff Schulwerk teacher is an artist and improviser who tailors the learning pathway for each child or class of students (Keetman, 1974). Rather than conducting students or directing learning each step of the way, the Orff Schulwerk teacher often acts more as a facilitator of the music-making process, inviting students to contribute ideas and make musical decisions (Beegle & Bond, 2016). Similarly, people who teach popular music using processes such as these exhibit the qualities of flexibility and responsiveness as well (Vasil, 2015). Both Orff Schulwerk and popular music teachers step in when students need help and know when to hold back and let students solve their own musical problems (Boespflug, 2004; Bowman, 2004).

Music from children's cultures

Though a great deal of variety is available, Orff Schulwerk teachers often choose repertoire from their students' musical heritage and culture. Mindful Orff Schulwerk teachers understand that first using familiar music with children is the best way to connect them to unfamiliar music (Warner, 1991). Similarly, popular music teachers believe that starting with songs students know is the most natural way to lead them to explore pieces they do not know. Often this involves both teacher and student researching the musical artists who inspired the musician a student enjoys. Some educators viewing musical heritage more broadly believe popular music has become the new common musical heritage for children and adolescents in the United States (Vasil, 2015; Woody, 2011).

Orff and Keetman (1950–54) developed the *Music for Children* volumes within the context of mid-20th-

century German culture, and over the years, these materials have been adapted for many different countries using different folk repertoire. Carl Orff (1963) noted the importance of drawing on children's native cultural repertoire: "It wasn't simply a question of translation, but rather of using a country's folklore, its nursery rhymes and children's songs in the same way as the German ones have been used in the original" (p. 74). Margaret Murray, for example, adapted British rhymes for the English editions.

When properly vetted, popular music and dance can inspire a broad range of fun and educational movement experiences within the classroom that connect with children's broader culture.

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Though it makes sense to continue to include the art and folk music of children's cultures in the classroom, culture includes not only that of children's heritage, but also what children know from racial, religious, and social groups (Culture, 2019). Children's sonic landscape is entrenched in popular music—it is a critical part of their culture. When Orff and Keetman were developing the Schulwerk, media was not what it is today, nor was music as readily available at the touch of a finger. The rapid advancements in technology have made access to music faster and easier than ever before. Top 40 tunes can be heard throughout malls, grocery stores, restaurants, and at home. Streaming platforms provide instant access to millions of music tracks. Children today have the opportunity to hear a wider spectrum of music in a short period of time than someone could have heard in an entire lifetime a decade ago. Outside of school, they can have broad listening experiences via streaming services, a shared listening history of Top 40 tunes, and specific cultural and social listening experiences from their friends and family. Why not include music they know as a starting point in the classroom?

Musical characteristics

With the understanding that popular music is part of children's musical lives, it is interesting to note that the playground chants, folk music, and selections from the *Music for Children* volumes share many characteristics with popular music. The elemental characteristics of the Schulwerk parallel much of those in popular music: simple form, ostinati

patterns, and simple shifting harmony. The folk and world repertoire found within a typical Orff Schulwerk curriculum is mostly pentatonic and diatonic, with repetitive melodic and rhythmic patterns (Orff, 1978). Orff Schulwerk teachers analyze this to determine how to break pieces into parts they can easily teach by rote. Popular music often has repeating ostinato patterns and simple form as well. Though the tonality is largely diatonic, many modal and pentatonic popular songs exist. As with other repertoire, the elemental qualities of popular music make it easy to break down pieces and teach by rote, as well as invite improvisation and composition in the classroom.

Creativity

What is popular music but an ever-evolving, creative collection of boundary-pushing genres? Creativity is at the heart of both Orff Schulwerk and popular music education, whether in the form of arranging, improvising, or composing. Like Orff Schulwerk teachers, teachers of popular music help students move from imitation to exploration to creation. For example, a teacher leads children to imitate on ukulele a two-chord progression used in a popular song. Then the teacher guides the class in writing a song using those same two chords, but in a different order and played for a different length of time, exploring the material. Finally, students write their own song using the two chords with their choice of order and duration, but now moving into the realm of creation. Of note, Rodriguez (2004) recognized that student compositions are popular music, as the new piece of music is generated from the social history and culture of students and is constantly evolving.

Bringing Popular Music into Orff Schulwerk Classrooms

Recognizing the overlaps between the Schulwerk and popular music teaching and learning lays the foundation for identifying practical strategies for integrating the two in kindergarten through Grade 5 Orff Schulwerk music classrooms. Two simple strategies for doing this are moving to popular music and covering popular songs using classroom instruments.

Moving to popular music

One of the easiest ways to begin incorporating popular music is through movement. It can be used

the Dust (see Figure 1, p. 27). Here, scored for recorders and tubanos, the arrangement includes the melody of the chorus (A section) and verse (B section), and the piece is expanded through an improvisation section (C) in G pentatonic. The limited tone set lays particularly well for young recorder players, and the song is even more popular today since the release of the movie *Bohemian Rhapsody* in 2018. To introduce the C section, the teacher models slow quarter-quarter-half note phrases in G pentatonic that the students echo. The teacher provides time for students to work on creating their own patterns and invites soloists for the final run-through of the piece.

Songs with melodic and rhythmic ostinati work well for covers. As Jimmy Fallon and the Roots illustrate, traditional classroom instruments can be effective, though teachers can also consider replicating the timbres used in the original song by going beyond the Orff instrumentarium. For example, when Glen Chilcote, a music teacher at Kipps Elementary in Virginia, had his after-school Orff ensemble cover Herbie Hancock's *Chameleon*, a child played the "bass guitar" on an electric piano to imitate the original timbre.

A teaching sequence so commonly used in the Orff approach—imitate-explore-create—works just as well with popular music as with other genres.

A teaching sequence so commonly used in the Orff approach—imitate-explore-create—works just as well with popular music as with other genres. Elemental pieces of popular music invite aural learning, improvisation, and composition. Additionally, if a teacher includes music that students choose or listen to, there is instant "buy-in" and familiarity. As Lawton (2019) stated, popular music is a great way to keep students' attention and bring that element of "cool" into the classroom (p. 30).

Choosing the music

To bring popular music into an Orff Schulwerk classroom, it is important to consider repertoire selection. As teachers, we need to note our students' musical preferences by asking them to name some of their favorite songs or by perusing sites such as the KidzBop YouTube channel for ideas of what is popular in the moment. Though this is a good starting place for reference, a better option is for

teachers to listen to the original performances of songs listed on the KidzBop channel, because the channel itself includes covers and "cleaned-up" versions of songs that may lack authenticity and musicality, making them less appealing than the original, even to children. We as teachers need to take the time to choose songs appropriate for school and use the original version, if possible. If the words or meaning are not appropriate for school, we can then choose another song by the same artist.

Another option is using a parody of a song. For example, I recently created a play-along for ukulele in the style of Billie Eilish's *Bad Guy* because my students unanimously indicated this was a favorite song. It has merit for the classroom—it recently won Song of the Year at the Grammy Awards and follows a simple repeating chord sequence—though the original lyrics and music video are not appropriate for school. Instead, I found a parody of the song from the children's show *All That*, where the words were rewritten to be about villains from comic books and movies (e.g., the Wicked Witch of the West and Voldemort from *Harry Potter*). Additionally, if a song is in another language, consider consulting a friend who is fluent in that language or carefully research the translation of the song online.

For movement lessons, make sure the music is at an appropriate tempo for comfortable movement (keep in mind that children like to move faster than most adults). And when selecting music to cover on instruments, analyze the music—what is the mode? Are there simple ostinati? Is the harmony shifting or repetitive? Do the musical elements complement your specific music-learning objectives?

Last, include popular music you enjoy as well. Children know immediately if their teachers do not like a piece of music and will respond accordingly. When thoughtfully selected, a wealth of appealing and relevant repertoire is available. It takes time, a bit of creativity, and a willingness to meet students where they are to include music they prefer in the classroom.

Conclusion

Including music meaningful to children is at the core of the Schulwerk philosophy. Although it is time consuming, it is worthwhile to ask children about their interests and to investigate and analyze popular music. When teachers recognize and elevate knowledge students already hold and value, they and their students become partners in learning.

Popular music, trending continuously with time and culture, is here to stay; it should be included in the curriculum. Overlapping learning and teaching processes, such as imitate-explore-create, and the elemental characteristics of both, provide a seamless transition of popular music into the Orff Schulwerk

classroom. Be encouraged and inspired. Popular music has merit all its own. Just as cultural diversity is embraced within our classrooms, we need to be brave and get comfortable learning alongside our students to bring popular music into the classroom as well. ■

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